

Return of CFA: Call-Site Sensitivity Can Be Superior to Object Sensitivity Even for Object-Oriented Programs (Artifact Manual)

Our paper claims that call-site sensitivity is generally superior to object sensitivity. This artifact aims to reproduce the results in Table 2~6 which experimentally show that call-site sensitivity (e.g., *1callH+SL*) is more precise than existing state-of-the-art object sensitivities (e.g., *1objH+T*). Section 1 provides instructions to check whether the artifact is installed correctly. Section 2 illustrate how to reproduce the results in our paper. Section 3 explains how to analyze other programs with our artifact (Section 3.1) and how to analyze a program with a user-defined tunneling abstraction (Section 3.2).

1 Getting Started Guide

1.1 Setup

We provide our artifact in a VirtualBox (version 6.0) image with all of the libraries installed.

- ID: “popl2022” / PASSWORD: “1234”
- The artifact is located at the folder “**artifact**”, where you can find two pointer analyzers:
 - **doop**: This folder contains a Doop framework, which is modified to provide context tunneling. It can reproduce the results in Table 2, 3, 4, and 6. We integrated our technique to the artifact of “Precise and Scalable Points-to Analysis via Data-Driven Context Tunneling”¹.
 - **doop_tb15**: Another Doop framework that can reproduce the result in Table 5. This folder uses the artifact of “Precision-Guided Context Sensitivity For Pointer Analysis”².

1.2 Verifying Installation (Basic Testing)

Move to the directory “~/artifact/doop”. Then, run the following command, which analyzes a program `luindex` with :

```
$ ./run.py 1callH+SL luindex
```

If the artifact is successfully installed, you will see the following results:

```
running dacapo benchmark: luindex
Main-Class: dacapo.luindex.Main
...
MBBENCH logicblox START
elapsed time: 42.27s
MBBENCH logicblox STOP
...
var points-to                250,012 (insens) / 2,930,383 (sens)
reachable casts that may fail 357
call graph edges             36,578 (insens) / 363,253 (sens)
reachable methods            7,710 (insens) / 80,760 (sens)
polymorphic virtual call sites 908
disk footprint (with stats) (KB) 351,232
```

¹ <https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3276931/abs/>

² <https://yuelee.bitbucket.io/software/zipper/>

The above results illustrate that *1callH+SL* takes 42.27 seconds. The results also show the results for the five client clients (VarPointsTo, #may-fail casts, #call-graph-edges, #reachable-methods, #poly-call sites, metric) used in Table 2 and 3. The analysis time can be different from the paper due the difference in experimental setting. In our paper, all the experiments are conducted on a machine with Intel i7 CPU and 64GB of RAM.

2 Reproducing Results in our paper

In this section, we present instructions for reproducing the result in Table 2~6. To reproduce Table 2~6, move to “~/artifact/doop”.

2.1 Reproducing the Result in Table 2, 3, 4, and 6

Following the instruction below reproduces the result in Table 2, 3, 4, and 6. The command for analyzing a program <pgm> with an analysis <analysis> is as follows:

```
$ ./run.py <analysis> <pgm>
```

<analysis> can be one of the following analysis:

```
1callH+SL, 1callH+S, 1objH+T, 2objH+T, 1callH+T, 1callH+SL_, 1callH+S_, S1objH+T,
DecisionTree, 1callH+T_new
```

where *1callH+SL_* and *1callH+S_* correspond to *1callH+SL'* and *1callH+S'* in Table 6, respectively. *DecisionTree* and *1callH+T_new* will reproduce the results in Table 4. <pgm> can be one of the following benchmarks:

```
luindex, lusearch, antlr, pmd, eclipse, xalan,
chart, fop, bloat, jython, jpc, checkstyle
```

If you want to analyze *eclipse* with *1callH+SL*, type:

```
$ ./run.py 1callH+SL eclipse
```

If you want to analyze all the benchmarks with *1callH+SL*, type:

```
$ ./run.py 1callH+SL -all
```

Note that if you use call-site sensitivity using our simulation technique (i.e., *1callH+S* or *1callH+S_*), it first runs a baseline analysis (*1objH+T* or *S1objH+T*). Then, run call-site sensitivity with a simulated tunneling abstraction (~/artifact/doop/TunnelingAbstraction.facts) computed from the baseline analysis.

2.2 Reproducing the Result in Table 5

To reproduce the result in Table 5, move to “~/artifact/doop.tb15”. The instruction below reproduces the result in Table 5.

```
$ ./run.py <analysis> <pgm>
```

<analysis> can be one of the following analysis:

```
1callH+SL, 1callH+SLZ, 2objH+Z
```

`1callH+SL`, `1callH+SLZ`, and `2objH+Z` correspond to *1callH+SL*, *1callH+SL+Zip*, and *2objH+Zip* in Table 5, respectively. `<pgm>` can be one of the benchmarks in Table 5:

```
eclipse, bloat, chart, sunflow, checkstyle, sunflow09,
avrora09, fop, jpc, xalan, findbugs, batik, xalan09, h2
```

If you want to analyze a program `eclipse` with `1callH+SL`, type:

```
$ ./run.py 1callH+SL eclipse
```

If you want to analyze all the benchmarks with `1callH+SL`, type:

```
$ ./run.py 1callH+SL -all
```

3 Reusing Our Artifact for Other Programs or Future Research

In this section, we illustrate how to use our artifact for analyzing other programs or reuse our artifact for future research (e.g., analyzing a program with a user-defined tunneling abstraction).

3.1 Analyzing Other Programs

First, move to `'~/artifact/door/'`. The following command will run our DOOP:

```
$ ./run -jre1.6 <analysis> <pgm.jar>
```

Note that the command uses `./run` rather than `./run.py` used in Section 2. `<analysis>` can be an analysis as follows:

- 1-tunneled-call-site-sensitive+heap
- 1-tunneled-object-sensitive+heap
- 2-object-sensitive+heap
- selective-1-tunneled-object-sensitive+heap
- ...

`<pgm.jar>` can be your jar file to be analyzed. For example, to analyze `program.jar` with *1callH+SL*, type:

```
$ ./run -jre1.6 1-tunneled-call-site-sensitive+heap program.jar
```

3.2 Analyzing Programs with a Custom Tunneling Abstraction

You can also analyze a program with your own tunneling abstraction. To do so, you need to modify `TunnelingAbstraction.facts` file. The file is located in `'~/artifact/door/'`. It includes a set of invocation sites that will be tunneled during the analysis. After the modification, type:

```
$ ./run -jre1.6 1-call-site-sensitive+heap+tunneling program.jar
```

For example, if you modified `TunnelingAbstraction.facts` to include empty set (e.g., `$ echo "" > TunnelingAbstraction.facts`), `program.jar` will be analyzed under conventional 1-call-site-sensitivity without context tunneling. If you modify `TunnelingAbstraction.facts` to include all the invocation sites in `program.jar`, the program will be analyzed without updating contexts (e.g., context-insensitive analysis) as all the method calls are tunneled. The challenge in context tunneling is to find a suitable tunneling abstraction (e.g., suitable set of invocation sites) that would maximize the precision. You can also run 1-object sensitivity with your tunneling abstraction by typing the following command:

```
$ ./run -jre1.6 1-object-sensitive+heap+tunneling program.jar
```